

MODERN METHODS OF INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF GRADUATES OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Providing high-quality and competitive educational services in higher education is an important issue that first of all requires a systematic study of the public education system. This, in turn, includes planning the processes of providing educational services as a component of social services.

Providing high-quality and competitive educational services in higher education is an important issue that first of all requires a systematic study of the public education system. This, in turn, includes planning the processes of providing educational services as a component of social services. That is: conducting a complex of marketing researches of the national and regional markets of educational services of higher education, as well as the market of secondary special and vocational education;

study of national and regional labor markets to understand the most demanding and priority areas of training of highly qualified specialists;

to study the level of satisfaction of employers in the republic and some regions with the quality and results of training graduates in higher educational institutions; adaptation, improvement of traditional specialties and introduction of new specialties required by the national and regional economy. Another important component of the scheme of high-quality and competitive educational service delivery processes of higher education is the component related to the design of educational service delivery processes by the university.

The development of training programs is carried out on the basis of selected educational specialties, taking into account the requirements of current educational standards and taking into account the requirements of regional employers. These include methodological, staffing and software development for the provision of educational services, such as lesson planning for students, etc.

Offering a package of services in higher education, first of all, the established criteria for further internships of partner enterprises, various training centers aimed at retraining staff

and teachers who publish basic and basic educational literature for inclusion in the library fund. ; is an important issue related to the selection of the suppliers of the required training equipment and finally the different groups of applicants for training in the training programs being implemented. This component, as part of the scheme, provides for the rational organization of direct educational processes at the university and providing them with all the necessary resources necessary for the implementation of the processes intended for the provision of educational services in higher education. The next component of the scheme of processes for providing high-quality and competitive educational services of higher education "Modeling and management of the main infrastructure objects of the University" is related to the implementation of a set of processes aimed at creating an adequate educational system. In this process, the necessary infrastructure complex of the university, which makes the process of using educational services convenient and continuous, is important. Practice shows that the more developed and diverse the infrastructure complex of the university, the higher the level of satisfaction of students with the use of educational services of higher education institutions, and the more systematic the process of forming students' competencies.

The final component of the processes of providing high-quality and competitive educational services of higher education is directly the component "Providing educational services of higher education", within which the main educational and educational processes are carried out. will be increased, will end with students achieving the planned results of being at the university. In addition, through the feedback of the target audience, the necessity and the main direction of reengineering the university's educational and educational processes will be determined. The presented structural structure of the components of the scheme of high-quality and competitive educational service delivery processes allows us to define the following characteristics and results of the educational service delivery processes of higher education. Features of the processes of providing high-quality and competitive educational services of higher education:

- the main direction of the studied processes is aimed at ensuring the reproduction of intellectual resources, which significantly increases the level of requirements for professional skills in the conditions of the modern economy. workers and employees of the university;

- systematic implementation of the distribution of consumers of educational services of higher education into external and internal consumers, which allows universities to model different directions, content and quality levels of educational programs, which, in turn, , making quality assessment processes inevitable. educational services conducted outside the university based on expert-analytical research, including evaluation;

- to ensure the multi-functionality of all educational services provided in higher education for the further integration and simultaneous implementation of educational, educational and educational functions at the university in order to increase the level of competitiveness, qualification and patriotism of the specialists being trained;

- not to the benefits of individual consumers, but to consumers of educational services of higher education, which is related to the socially oriented approach to the implementation of education and educational activities carried out by modern universities of our country and the world. strategic focus on specific groups;

- in modern society, education is perceived as a result of the consumption of educational services of higher education, and the university to a certain extent plays a decisive, but not the main, role in the formation of education.

In the process of providing educational services, great attention is paid to ensuring high-quality interaction of students with the external socio-economic environment, which is reflected in the content of the university's educational programs; -

The significant duration of the period of providing educational services of higher education institutions, which makes the full cycle of the implementation of educational programs of the university variable and unstable, in the context of possible changes in state educational standards. teaching staff and staff, regulatory and legal framework, methodological and information support, forces the target audience to make high demands on the level of formation of the university infrastructure complex, the university teaches to take into account all the changes that are taking place in higher education provides

As mentioned above, the special feature of providing educational services of higher education institutions is related to deep socio-economic orientation of these services. In addition, the field of higher education, which is seen as the conductor of all the progressive and new in the life of the state, business and society, often has a conservative base. Here under the conservatism of higher education should be understood selection, as well as careful preservation of the best foreign and domestic traditions and experiences in the field of educational services. Also, the competitive processes between universities as service enterprises exist and are manifested. As a rule, all leading universities have long-standing traditions in the field of higher education and have a unique history that is attractive to the target audience. Many universities do not need and do not carry out additional advertising of their educational services, and these universities carefully protect their image, because the status of universities can change for the worse or for the better by the public. changes are not ignored. Finally, in a country dominated by a planned economy, there was no need to conduct a continuous economic and marketing assessment of the current and future competitive position of the university, since the general state planning defines and determines the place and role of each specific university. is an element of the higher education system in the country.

Later, the changed socio-economic conditions of doing business put new goals and tasks for universities as service enterprises, and universities gained more freedom in implementing their educational plans. As a result, today there is no single conceptual approach to defining the essence of the term "competitiveness of the university as a service industry enterprise". This situation significantly complicates the development of reasonable methodological approaches to the analysis, evaluation, and regulation of the university's educational activities in relation to the environment of the modern education market in the world and in our country.

When studying the concept of competitiveness, V. N. Romanov defines the following important definition of this term: "Competitiveness should be understood as a set of consumer and price characteristics that determine the national or regional success of goods." Another author Ambartsumov.A.A. also adheres to the same position: "Competitiveness is the

sum of various consumption characteristics of goods, which determines their difference from other similar goods." In turn, A. V. Busigin emphasizes the following: "When developing different products, it is necessary to take into account the possible interdependence of the modern life cycles of similar products of other enterprises." In these definitions, the concept of competitiveness is presented as a sum of product characteristics, while these definitions take into account aspects related to the understanding that today consumers are more interested in the possible level of price-quality ratio can't. Of greatest interest is the possible level of the "price-quality" ratio. From these positions, it is important to apply the following definition to modern product markets, including the market of educational services of higher education: the level of competitiveness - the quality indicators of these goods and the significantly higher ratio of their purchase and consumption compared to the competitors, it is necessary to take into account the requirements of the market, the competitive goods, services for them the level of cumulative beneficial effect on a certain cost unit is much higher than others, and the cost of any characteristic of goods, services is not considered unacceptable for target consumers.

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